

ESTIMATION OF LIFE EXPERIENCES AMONG PREGNANT WOMEN DURING COVID-19 IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

COVID-19 came with serious afflictions which affected every aspect of the human life and every nation of the world. The effects of COVID-19 were faced and experienced by pregnant women across the world. This qualitative research considered a qualitative estimation of life experiences of pregnant women in Uyo metropolis, in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Estimation theory was considered by the researchers as theoretical framework for the study. A total of 30 sample size made up of pregnant women, nurses and midwives who were selected through snowballing and respondent's driven sampling technique were engaged in the study. Data were collected through in-depth interviews and key informant interviews. Findings of the study shown that during the COVID-19, the pregnant women were under intense anxiety, fear, worried and stressed. Also, pregnant women couldn't have access to health care services at the initial stage of the lockdown. Though there were difficulties, but at time, pregnant women got to enjoy staying at home during lockdown and were relieved of stress of certain works. Among others, the researchers recommended that there should be general mobilization of the health system for alleviating pregnant women's difficulties in situations like the COVID-19 epidemic, and there should be virtual training classes and virtual counseling to enhance the peace and tranquility of pregnant women in such situation.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19, estimation, life experiences, health care, and pregnant women

INTRODUCTION

According to WHO (2017), pregnancy period in a woman's life is characterized by various challenging, thus, exposing the woman to most vulnerability. The challenges are

always associate with factors such as social, economic, cultural, demographic and environmental. A catalogue of some of these related challenges that affects women while in pregnancy bothered on the economic status of their family, believe system, location of hospital etc. an appraisal of a catalogue of diseases such as that prevailed among human population shows that they have greater impact on the pregnant women (Mead, 2018). At the onset of the COVID-19 epidemic, pregnancy and childbirth for women took place in unusual circumstances. Studies of pregnant women during the COVID-19 period shows that they were mostly affected during the pandemic period. Pregnancy is one of the most pleasant and at the same time most critical periods in the life of most women. It involves a host of new and unprecedented emotions and experiences. Unfortunately, with the onset of the COVID-19 epidemic, pregnancy and childbirth for women takes a new dimension and unusual circumstances (Glatter and Finkelman, 2020).

A number of issues led to a state of confusion and anxiety among pregnant women during the crisis period. Among these, the most concerning were the continuous stream of news reports about rising number of infections and the increasing number of severe cases and death among childbearing women (Dong and Zheng, 2020). Other concerning issues ranges from emotional, physical, and mental exhaustion, as well as loss of medical staff. However, factors like shortage of essential hygiene equipment, the varieties of symptoms and secondary diseases caused by the infection, and the failure of many proposed treatments also posed some challenges to the system (Corbett, *et al*, 2020). Furthermore, the dissemination of false information on online platforms has played a part in creating high levels of fear and anxiety among pregnant women (Ahmad and Murad, 2020). Apart from socio-economic factors which affects the women which were as a results of their families (Ononokpono *et al*, 2020), other issues such as higher risk of contracting COVID – 19, vulnerability to severe complications, the risk of death, the risk of mother-to-child transmission (Di Mascio, *et al.*, 2020) and the potential effects of COVID-19 on the fetus were also serious problems affecting women (Zaigham and Andersson, 2020).

Studies shows that in previous epidemics, for instance, the great Influenza of 1920, Spanish flu of 1920, HIV/AIDS 1981-dates, Swine flu 2009, Ebola 2013 etc. 'the pregnant women were among the most vulnerable groups that suffered badly during this period (Brooks, *et al*, 2020; Shorey and Chan, 2020)'. However, during the severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) outbreak in Hong Kong, pregnant women were exposed to severe challenges like frustration, anxiety, problems with sleeping, and disruption of their daily lives (Dodgson, *et al*, 2010). Studies show that women were reluctant to attend hospitals for fear of infection. They also experienced insecurity and uneasiness even at home and had worries about contracting the disease (Lee, *et al*, 2006).

Evidence based in studies in Taiwan revealed the situation in other parts of the world. For instance, hospitals in Taiwan did not provide prenatal care and women were discharged early after childbirth despite the prevalence of disease COVID-19 (WHO, 2020). There was also a significant increase in the number of cesarean (Lee, *et al*, 2005). In the H1N1 pandemic, pregnant women reported worries about the future of their health and the risk of their babies as well as close acquaintances being infected by the virus. Some women felt it was not safe to go to work anymore and stayed at home (Lohm *et al*, 2014). In the Zika virus epidemic, women were affected by feelings of anxiety, helplessness and mistrust, and uncertainty about the new disease (Linde and Siqueira, 2018). Findings also shows that

during the Ebola epidemic, women avoided going to health centers because they were afraid of contracting the disease, and health care facilities also refused to provide services to pregnant women because of the risk that they might have carried the virus (Strong and Schwartz, 2019). So, similar problems were expected to occur for pregnant women as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic. Fear, anxiety, and worry during pregnancy has negative health consequences for both pregnant women and the growing fetus (Saisto, *et al* 2001). In Akwa Ibom State, the situations especially with regard to pregnant women need demographic estimation of their experiences which is the gap this work set to fill. However, since the outbreak of COVID-19, the experience of pregnant women that were not infected has not been investigated. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to estimate experiences of pregnant women during the COVID-19 period in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Estimation Theory

According Loskot (2014), Estimation Theory has the following sections:

Random versus non-random parameters

parameter(s) of interest unknown, so must be estimated

if a priori statistical description of parameter(s) completely (fully) known, then treat them as random (and unknown)

if no a priori description of parameters known, then treat them as non-random (and unknown)

however, a priori statistics of parameters often known partially (e.g. only mean values, and variances known), or their statistical description has unknown parameters (e.g. variance unknown); these cases cannot be treated as estimation of random or non-random parameters

Optimum versus sub-optimum estimators:

- optimum (general) estimator may be too complex, or some important knowledge is missing (e.g. some parameters of a priori statistics not known) sub-optimum estimator may still be optimum but only within a certain (e.g.linear) class or under implementation (maximum complexity) constraints

Optimality criterion of estimators:

- understand the purpose of estimating (i.e. knowing) the parameter(s)
- define (i.e. quantify) the estimation error, and then obtain optimum estimator to minimize this error; however, in some cases, no such estimator may exist

Time-varying parameters:

- such parameters can be considered to be signals, so their estimation of time-varying parameters is referred to as signal filtering Wiener and Kalman filters are most well-known linear estimators of signals

Nuisance parameters:

- measured signal is often function of parameters of interest (to be estimated) and other (so-called nuisance) parameters not of interest but which cannot simply be ignored.
- random nuisance parameters can be eliminated (averaged out) from the estimator, or non-random nuisance parameters are first estimated prior to parameter of interest estimation (this is referred to as adaptive estimation), or nuisance parameters are also

estimated and then simply ignored

General estimation: random parameters

Notation:

P unknown parameter (random variable, RV)

p particular value of RV P

$X(P)$ measured value is RV as it is function of RV P

$x(p)$ particular value of X as function of $P=p$

$\hat{P}(X)$ parameter estimate is RV as it is function of RV

$f_{X|P}(x|p)$ or $\Pr_{X|P}(x|p)$ conditional PDF or conditional probability

Assumptions:

- a priori PDF $f_P(p)$ or PMF $\Pr_P(p)$ is known
- statistical description of X as a function of (parametrized by) P is known, i.e., $f_{X|P}(x|p)$ or $\Pr_{X|P}(x|p)$ is known
- P and X are scalar RVs; extension to random vectors (often) straight forward

Note that:

- although $X(P)$, for simplicity, we may write only X
- although $\hat{P}(X)$, for simplicity, we may write only \hat{P} (Loskot, 2014)

Though the theory can be seen as a quantitative approach of disease and disease management estimation, the research work being a qualitative research, drive the theory through qualitative estimation procedure in thematic estimation based on the reports and narratives of the study participants in accordance to the subject matters of the research.

METHODOLOGY

The study which was qualitative was conducted on pregnant women who were registered in public health centers in ST. Luke Hospital Anua, Primary Health Centre Ofot, and University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, all within Uyo metropolis. Sampling technique was snowballing and respondents driven technique. Four midwives each working in one of the purposively chosen health centers within Uyo metropolis were directed to contact through snowballing, eligible pregnant women registered with them to participate in the study. Interviews were conducted through WhatsApp chats, and the length of each interview was 25–30 min through the WhatsApp social network. 30 women were interviewed. We also conducted virtual interview with the midwives to observe hygiene protocols. Gathered data were analysed thematically. The participating women were already pregnant as at the time of the first signs the epidemic appeared in Nigeria as well as at the time of the interview. We collected data through in-depth interviews and key informant interview as we sought understanding of the experiences of the pregnant during COVID-19 pandemic in 2020

RESULTS

Intense Stress

The finding indicates that pregnant women were under intense stress for the first few weeks after the official confirmation of the epidemic in the country. This stress rose as the infection and mortality rates also increase. According to one of the participants, in her narrative, she reported that;

Since the beginning of this problem call COVID-19, we have suffered so much that life is becoming so stressful that sometimes I want to regret getting pregnant before now. But I didn't know that there will be this kind of stressful problem where you are no longer free to go to where you use to or supposed to go nor do what you suppose to do. It is not ease oh.

Fear of Infection

It was also discovered that pregnant women were highly afraid of becoming infected in the time of their pregnancy and childbirth. Since the health of a fetus and its mother is inseparable, this fear was mostly for the safety and health of the baby. The women avoided busy places such as hospitals, for fear of miscarriage due to the corona-virus, and of their children or companions becoming infected in the hospitals. One of the key informants narrated that;

Our registered patients especially the pregnant women are no longer coming to hospital as they used to even when there has been announcement in the radio and other media means to encourage them to come to the hospital for safe delivery, some of them are afraid of contacting the virus which they are told is more dangerous than HIV. So there is so much fear among pregnant women and this has affected their responses to coming to the hospital

Anxiety

Cases of anxiety were also reported. The pregnant women were aware of the effects of stress in times of pregnancy. They had heard that a pregnant woman is more vulnerable towards COVID-19 compared to others. In some of the cases, pregnancy itself was high risk for the women, and this really worries them. Another source of distress for women was that, since the beginning of the pandemic, hospitals no longer allowed entry to companions and family members as before. The pregnant women also experienced other worries (as experienced by non-pregnant individuals), such as their husbands or older and sickly family members becoming infected. In some ways, the worry for the husbands becoming infected was because of the close nature of husband/wife relationship, and in reality, a worry for the woman herself to get infected as a result of her going to the hospital. Some were also thinking about the possibility that the infection can pass to the infant through breastfeeding. One of the study participants in her narrative reported that;

To go to the hospital these days, me I am afraid because I don't want to get infected with their virus and you know my husband can longer follow me to the hospital because they said that we must observed social distance, and even if my husband come, he can be infected and our baby might be infected if I put to birth at the hospital. Because infected people are taken to the hospital. Me I am afraid, please.

Sense of Loneliness and Lack of Support

Findings also indicate that the pregnant women felt that they were not being

sufficiently supported during this epidemic. They complained of the closing of the clinics, the push to make women avoid visiting health centers, and the lack of health-package allocation to pregnant women. This also account for the emotional pressure the women experienced. One of the key informants reported that;

I don't know who is telling them that hospital is close and we can't attend to pregnant women now. You wouldn't belief that so many pregnant women still believe that hospitals are still close and we can't attend to them. But as it is, the government should see how to support the pregnant women especially at times like this. Some of these pregnant women are complaining of lack of government packages for them in order to ease their plight.

Depression and Loneliness in Quarantine

Observably, although quarantine had resulted in the decrease of stress and obsession among the pregnant women, it had also resulted in the experience of loneliness and depression. One of the key informants at University of Uyo Teaching Hospital narrated that:

We had some pregnant women in the hospital before the lock down, and we were instructed to keep them, quarantine them through their delivery and we did that. These women after delivery felt so lonely and depressed as family members couldn't come for them and those they did expect to pay them visit couldn't come to the hospital because of the lock down. But when the government started responding to those women in support, it ease a bit of their depression, but they were still feeling lonely.

New Challenges Caused by the Epidemic

Records show that the epidemic caused a lot of problems for the pregnant women. Some of the problems were as in acquiring health products, and lack of open health care facilities which also amount to challenges causes by the epidemic. In the beginnings of the epidemic, there was a noticeable shortage of health products such as hygiene gels and masks in the hospitals, health centers, and pharmacies. The period also records a noticeable cost of products and services which affects the behaviour of patients.

Women mentioned during interviews mentioned some disruptions in receiving health-care in the beginnings of the epidemic such as cancellation of pregnancy-related appointments, the closing-down of some specialist and private offices, the wait-times for visits in hospitals, and the crowds of visitors in sonography and other types of clinics all disrupts health-care services. One of the study participants during her narratives reported that;

You know that COVID-19 caught with us when we were not prepared for it and it made life very difficult for everybody. But our cases were different as we couldn't go for antenatal services and some health centres did not open until after some times. It was difficult to get our routine drugs and some needed

items for delivery. But thank God we survive it all.

Antenatal preparatory classes which have become a common practice in recent years to prepare women for the event of childbirth were no more in practice for reason of contact. Usually,

Adaptation with New Conditions

The findings show that the level of stress has decreased as time passed. Some of the women spoke of reductions in their stress levels and obsessive behaviour, as they were able to adjust to the reality. The findings equally indicate that they were able to regulate their levels of adherence to the sanitation protocols. For communication between pregnant women and midwives, creation of a WhatsApp social media group was one of the methods adopted by the women during the COVID-19 crisis. Pregnant women's responses to the creation of the WhatsApp online group were generally positive and welcoming by all, as they used the medium in sharing information with each other and the nurses/midwives. This group comprised of pregnant women, midwives from health care facilities, and some other faculty members. The one-time preparatory classes were also conducted through this internet provision service. According to one of the key informants;

We had to find a way to communicate the pregnant women and we found out that the best way was to create a whatsapp group for them. Though it was not every of the women that had android phone, some used their husbands' phones while very few couldn't join because they did not have access to a phone with capacity for WhatsApp. But the innovation was very resultful as we were able to reach the women and passed needed information to them.

Findings also show that the pregnant women adhered to the quarantine very well. They stated that doing so reduced their stress and obsessive behaviour. It was noted that the pregnant women submitted themselves to self-quarantine by staying back in their houses to avoid contacting the virus and exposing themselves to health dangers. Also, the nutritional intake of the pregnant women during the COVID-19 period changed based on suggestions that were common in the beginning of the epidemic. One of the study participants narrated that;

We later enjoy staying at home as we were able to stay off stress and some works. We only eat fresh food from our small gardens near our houses as markets were not open and we were told by the nurses that it was better for us.

Some of these changes pregnant women adhered to during the COVID-19 lockdown period included abstaining from consuming bulk foodstuff and food from the outside (restaurants etc.), as well as consuming more cooked food and specific fruits and vegetables. This however affects positively the health of the mothers and of the babies.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings indicate that pregnant women experienced hardships and severe stress in their daily lives during the first weeks of the official announcement of the epidemic by the government and the quarantine period. Stress, fear, worry and anxiety, feelings of depression, and loneliness were found to be common among pregnant women during the epidemic. These findings were given credence by Ahorsu *et al*, 2020; Samadipour *et al*, 2020; Rajkumar, 2020 who posited that pregnant women during COVID-19 undergo through some forms of stress, anxiety, fear and worries. However, similar responses were also reported in pregnant women during the previous epidemics and pandemics before the COVID-19 (Dodgson *et al.*, 2010; Lee *et al*, 2006).

Pregnant women when compared to other groups of persons, have other concern in addition to their own health. However, findings revealed that women were concerned about the health of the fetus and having a healthy delivery. The further studies indicated that a higher percentage of pregnant women experienced extreme fear, anxiety, and depression during the COVID-19 epidemic compared to normal times (Yassa, *et al*, 2020; Ravaldi, *et al*, 2020). Moreover, main concern of pregnant women in this study was the possibility of being infected with COVID-19 and transferring the virus to the growing fetus. Findings of the study indicated that the possibility of giving birth to an abnormal/unhealthy baby was the most prevalent causes of worry and anxiety in pregnant women in normal conditions.

Emergence of findings showed that women sought to reduce their risk of infection through behavioural responses such as strict adherence to quarantine and health protocols and lifestyle changes. This finding supports Lee and You (2020) who reported that behavioural changes usually happen as a result of psychological experiences such as stress, fear and worry. According to the previous studies, pregnant women used behavioural strategies to lower their risk of getting SARS and Zika virus. (Dodgson *et al.*, 2010; Lee *et al.*, 2006).

Further findings of the study revealed that nurses found ways of communicating with the pregnant women in order to reduce stress. One of the ways they communicated was through the use of WhatsApp. The social media became an innovative means of communication between the nurses, midwives, other health officers and the pregnant women. This finding disagrees with WHO (2020) report that the news media and in particular the social media played a negative and harmful role at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic. Their coverage spread more distress and anxiety rather than more awareness and readiness for confronting the situation. There was also a large measure of distrust among most of the women with regard to the official statistics of COVID-19 cases announced by the Health Ministry. Findings from Samadipour and Ghardashi's (2020) online study indicate that more than 80% of participants in 20 provinces of the study area were distrustful of the authorities.

CONCLUSIONS

This qualitative study explored the experiences of pregnant women during the COVID-19 epidemic. In qualitatively estimating the life experiences of pregnant women during the COVID-19, the pregnant women were found to be under intense anxiety, fear, worried and stressed during the COVID-19 outbreak. The Lockdown brought about several

difficulties to the pregnant women by not allowing family members have access to their wives and daughters. Pregnant women had difficulties in accessing health facilities in some cases until there was news about the opening of all health care facilities for treatments. Nurses adopted social media mediums as means of communicating and reaching out to the pregnant women during the COVID-19.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study by the researchers, made the following recommendations;

1. The general mobilization of the health system is necessary for alleviating pregnant women's difficulties in situations like the COVID-19 epidemic.
2. Virtual training classes and virtual counseling may enhance the peace and tranquility of pregnant women.
3. Support from family members, during times like COVID-19 is necessary for alleviating stress and anxiety during pregnancy for pregnant women.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, A. R, and Murad H. R. (2020). The impact of social media on panic during the COVID-19 pandemic in Iraqi Kurdistan: online questionnaire study. *J Med Internet Res*. 22(5): e19556.
- Ahorsu, D. K, Imani V, Lin C-Y, Timpka T, Broström A, Updegraff J. A, Årestedt K, Griffiths MD, and Pakpour A. H. (2020); Associations between fear of COVID-19, mental health, and preventive Behaviours across pregnant women and husbands: an actor-partner interdependence Modelling. *Int J Ment Health Addiction*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11469-020-00340-x>.
- Austin Z and Sutton J. (2014); Qualitative research: getting started. *Can J Hosp Pharm*. ;67(6):436–40.
- Brooks SK, Weston D, and Greenberg N. (2020); Psychological impact of infectious disease outbreaks on pregnant women: rapid evidence review. *Public Health*.;189:26–36.
- Corbett G. A., Milne S. J., Hehir M. P, Lindow S.W., and O'connell M. P.(2020) Health anxiety and behavioural changes of pregnant women during the COVID-19 pandemic. *European Journal Obstetrics Gynecology Reproductive Biology* 249:96–7.
- Corbin J, Strauss A (2008); Basics of qualitative research (3rd ed.): techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452230153>.
- Di Mascio D, Khalil A, Saccone G, Rizzo G, Buca D, Liberati M, Vecchiet J, Nappi L, Scambia G, and Berghella V. (2020). Outcome of coronavirus spectrum infections (SARS, MERS, COVID-19) during pregnancy: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Am J Obstet Gynecol MFM*. 2020;2(2):100107.
- Dodgson J. E., Tarrant M., and Chee Y-O, Watkins A. (2010). New mothers' experiences of social disruption and isolation during the severe acute respiratory syndrome outbreak in Hong Kong. *Nursing Health Science* 2010;12(2):198–204.
- Dong M, and Zheng J. Letter to the editor: headline stress disorder caused by Netnews during the outbreak of COVID-19. *Health Expect*. 2020;23(2):259–60.

- Durankuş F, Aksu E. (2020); Effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on anxiety and depressive symptoms in pregnant women: a preliminary study. *Journal of Maternal Fetal Neonatal Medicine* <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767058.2020.1763946>:1-7.
- Glatter, K. and Fin Kelvin, P. (2020) History of the Plague and Ancient Pandemic for the age of Covid-19. *Am. J. Med Soc* 2-9343, 30792-30800. doi:10:1016y:anymad2020:08:019
- Hantoushzadeh S., Shamshirsaz A. A., Aleyasin A., Nouri B., Nekooghadam S. M., and Aagaard K. (2020); Maternal Death Due to COVID-19 Disease. *AJOG*. 223(1):109 e101–109.e116.
- Lee C-H, Huang N, Chang H-J, Hsu Y-J, Wang M-C, and Chou Y-J. (2005); The immediate effects of the severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) epidemic on childbirth in Taiwan. *BMC Public Health*. ;5(1):30.
- Lee DT, Sahota D, Leung TN, Yip AS, Lee FF, Chung TK. (2006). Psychological responses of pregnant women to an infectious outbreak: a case-control study of the 2003 SARS outbreak in Hong Kong. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research* 61(5):707–13.
- Lee M, You M.(2020); Psychological and behavioral responses in South Korea during the early stages of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). *International Journal of Environment and Research on Public Health*. 17(9):2977.
- Linde AR, Siqueira CE. (2018); Women s lives in times of Zika: mosquito-controlled lives? *Cadernos de Saúde Pública*. 34(5):e00178917. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0102-311x00178917>
- Lohm D, Flowers P, Stephenson N, Waller E, Davis MDM. (2014); Biography, pandemic time and risk: pregnant women reflecting on their experiences of the 2009 influenza pandemic. *Health*. ;18(5):493–508.
- Mead, P. S (2018). Plague in Madagascar-a tragic opportunity for improving public health. *N. England Journal of Medicine* 378, 106-108. doi:10.1056/NEJMp1713881
- Mortazavi F, Akaberi A (2018); Validation of the anxiety scale for pregnancy in a sample of Iranian women. *IJWHR*. 6(1):67–74.
- Mortazavi F, Akaberi A. (2016); Worries of Pregnant Women: Testing the Farsi Cambridge Worry Scale. *Scientifica*. 2016:5791560. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/5791560>.
- Ononokpono, D. N., Peters, M. I. and Usoro, N. A. (2020) Determinants of Health Care Utilization among Retirees in Rural Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *The Nigerian Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*. 18(1): 71-86
- Rajkumar RP. (2020); COVID-19 and mental health: a review of the existing literature. *Asian Journal of Psychiatric*. 52:102066.
- Ravaldi C, Wilson A, Ricca V, Homer C, Vannacci A. (2020); Pregnant women voice their concerns and birth expectations during the COVID-19 pandemic in Italy. *Women Birth*.. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wombi.2020.07.002>.
- Saisto T, Salmela-Aro K, Nurmi J-E, Halmesmäki E. (2001). Psychosocial characteristics of women and their partners fearing vaginal childbirth. *BJOG*. 2001;108(5):492–8. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-0528.00122.x> PMID: 11368135.
- Samadipour E, Ghardashi F. (2020): Factors influencing Iranians' risk perception of Covid-19. *Journal of Military Medicine* 22(2):122–9.
- Serafini G, Parmigiani B, Amerio A, Aguglia A, Sher L, Amore M. (2020); The psychological impact of COVID-19 on the mental health in the general population. *QJM*.;113(8):531–7.

- Shorey S, Chan V. (2020). Lessons from past epidemics and pandemics and a way forward for pregnant women, midwives and nurses during COVID-19 and beyond: a meta-synthesis. *Midwifery*. 90:102821.
- Strong A. E. and Schwartz D. A. (2019); Effects of the West African Ebola Epidemic on Health Care of Pregnant Women: Stigmatization With and Without Infection. In: Schwartz DA, Anoko JN, Abramowitz SA, editors. *Pregnant in the Time of Ebola: Women and Their Children in the 2013-2015 West African Epidemic*. Cham: Springer International Publishing. p. 11–30. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-97637-2_2.
- WHO (2017) Plague Availability Outline at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/plague> (accessed December 1, 2023)
- Yassa M, Birol P, Yirmibes C, Usta C, Haydar A, Yassa A, Sandal K, Tekin AB, Tug N. (2020); Near-term pregnant women's attitude toward, concern about and knowledge of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Maternal Fetal Neonatal Medicine* <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767058.2020.1763947:1-8>.
- Zaigham M, and Andersson O (2020); Maternal and perinatal outcomes with COVID-19: a systematic review of 108 pregnancies. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aogs.13867>.